

Broadband Photometric Constraints on the Age of the Triangulum Galaxy Core

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Abstract

We present a broadband photometric study of the central region of Messier 33 using CCD imaging obtained in the blue (B), visible (V), red (R), and infrared (I) bands at the Leuschner Optical Observatory. The observations were calibrated using standard bias, dark, and flat-field corrections, and sky-background subtraction was performed using dedicated offset sky frames. Integrated fluxes of the galaxy's core were measured in each band using region-sum photometry, yielding a four-point optical spectral energy distribution (SED). An independent B/V aperture-based diagnostic yields $F_B/F_V = 0.2485 \pm 0.0094$ (instrumental $(b - v) = 1.512 \pm 0.041$) to reinforce the red-dominant core spectrum. The resulting SED exhibits a statistically significant rise towards the R and I bands, with the B-V length remaining flat. This behavior is consistent with stellar populations dominated by cool, evolved stars. Comparison to published stellar population synthesis models suggests that the estimated age of M33's core is 10–13 Gyr.

1. INTRODUCTION

Messier 33 (M33), also known as the Triangulum Galaxy, is the third-largest member of the Local Group after the Milky Way and Andromeda. At a distance of ~ 2.7 Mpc (Freedman et al. 1991), M33 provides an important laboratory for studying galaxy formation and evolution in a low-mass, late-type spiral system. M33 is relatively face-on and exhibits minimal foreground extinction, making its stellar populations ideal for calibrating chemical evolution models, star-formation histories, and population-synthesis techniques (e.g., Corbelli & Thilker 2014; Galleti et al. 2004).

Although the global stellar populations of M33 have been extensively characterized, particularly in the disk and spiral arms using multi-wavelength photometry and resolved-star studies, its *central* regions remain comparatively under-constrained. Several previous efforts have constructed SEDs of M33 using large-aperture or integrated-light measurements (e.g., Thilker et al. 2005; Regan et al. 2015), but these typically emphasize galaxy-wide properties. High-resolution studies tend to focus either on individual clusters or on resolved asymptotic giant branch and red giant branch populations in the inner 1–2 kpc (Williams et al. 2009). As a result, a direct broadband characterization using the Johnson–Cousins $UBVRI$ photometric system remains a persistent gap in the literature. In this study, we will be using the $BVRI$ filter passbands of the inner core of M33 to estimate its luminosity-weighted stellar age.

Galaxy cores are particularly valuable for age-dating because they are dominated by old and dynamically mixed stellar populations. In late-type spirals, such as M33, whose central regions lack a classical bulge, the core light provides a relatively clean probe for ancient star-formation investigations (McConnachie 2012). Old, metal-rich populations exhibit SEDs that peak at red and near-infrared wavelengths, whereas younger populations have stronger blue and ultraviolet continua. Thus, broadband photometry across the $BVRI$ filters offers rough but effective means of constraining the dominant stellar ages.

To obtain multi-band imaging of the core, we conducted CCD observations of M33 using the 30-inch telescope at Leuschner Observatory (UC Berkeley Department of Astronomy 2024). The telescope is equipped with an SBIG STL-11000M CCD containing a 4008×2672 pixel KAF-11000 sensor. Multiple exposures were acquired in the $BVRI$ filters and calibrated using standard reduction procedures (bias subtraction, dark subtraction, flat-fielding). Reference

stars within the field were used to verify pointing stability, assess sky transparency, and evaluate potential atmospheric fluctuations during the observations.

In this work, we construct a relative *BVRI* SED of the central region of M33 and compare it with stellar population synthesis models to infer its dominant stellar age. We therefore also compute a simple *B/V* aperture-based core-color diagnostic as an internal consistency check on the short-wavelength SED slope, independent of absolute photometric calibration. This study provides a localized, directly observed constraint on the core’s stellar population, complementing existing large-scale SED analyses of the galaxy.

2. OBSERVATIONS AND DATA REDUCTION

2.1. Observational Setup

We observed the central region of M33 on November 16, 2024 between 19:00–22:00 PST using the 30-inch telescope at Leuschner Observatory (37.915° N, 122.105° W; elevation 300 m). The SBIG STL–11000M CCD, operated in 2×2 binning mode, provided a pixel scale of $0.335'' \text{ pixel}^{-1}$, and a field of view of $20' \times 13.4'$, sufficient to encompass the optical core of the galaxy. The observing night occurred 29 hours and 32 minutes (~ 29.53 hours) after the Moon reached peak illumination at 13:28 PST on November 15, 2024.

Five science exposures (“science frames”) were obtained in each of the *BVRI* filters, with an integration time of 120 s per frame. Frames showing flat-topped stellar profiles were discarded to avoid saturation. For each filter, an additional set of five sky frames was acquired by offsetting the telescope 11 jog steps from the galaxy to regions mostly free of bright stars or nebular emission; additional subtraction of remaining stars in the frames were applied for maximum omission of bright light. These sky frames were later used to subtract the sky-background from the science frames. Additionally, to track atmospheric transparency and pointing stability, several bright field stars surrounding the galaxy were monitored throughout data collection.

Throughout this paper, the terms “sky,” “sky-background,” and “background” refer to the diffuse night-sky brightness (moonlight, airglow, and scattered light) that adds an approximately uniform signal to each CCD exposure. Table 1 summarizes the observational parameters.

Table 1. Summary of Observational Parameters

Parameter	<i>B</i>	<i>V</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>I</i>	Notes
Number of science frames	5	5	5	5	no over-saturation
Number of sky frames	5	5	5	5	telescope jogged 11 steps
Exposure time (s)	120	120	120	120	fixed across filters
Airmass range	1.15–1.30	1.15–1.25	1.10–1.20	1.10–1.15	M33 rising
Moon phase					29.53 hours after full Moon
Target Right Ascension					RA = 01:33:50.9
Target Declination					Dec = +30:39:36.6
CCD System					SBIG STL–11000M (KAF–11000)
Pixel scale					$0.335'' \text{ pixel}^{-1}$, 2×2 binning
Field of view					$20' \times 13.4'$

2.2. Calibration Frames and Initial Processing

Standard CCD calibration procedures were applied to all images. Master bias, dark, and flat-field frames were constructed by median-combining the corresponding calibration exposures. Twilight flats were obtained in all four filters, and the *R*- and *I*-band flat fields were recorded in the CCD’s original unbinned mode. To ensure consistent application of the flat-field corrections across all filters, the *R*- and *I*-band master flats and flat-darks were resampled via bilinear interpolation to match the 2×2 binned science-frame pixel scale before flat-fielding.

Each science frame was then corrected according to the standard CCD calibration equation (Sec. 3.2), removing bias structure, dark current, and pixel-to-pixel sensitivity variations.

2.3. Background Subtraction

Although CCD calibration removes instrumental signatures, the calibrated science frames still contained significant large-scale sky brightness, especially in the R - and I -band. To remove this additive component, the sky frames for each filter were cleaned and combined to produce a master sky image. Each master sky frame was scaled to the modal background level of the corresponding science image and subtracted, effectively suppressing the diffuse sky contribution while retaining the galaxy’s extended emission.

2.4. Flux Extraction

After background subtraction, integrated fluxes of the central core region of M33 were measured using a fixed rectangular region enclosing the central light concentration in each frame. The same region was used for all filters to ensure consistent sampling of the core stellar population. This region-sum approach is well suited for mild saturation in the innermost I -band pixels and appropriate for extended, non-point-like sources.

Flux uncertainties were estimated by propagating photon-counting noise within the extraction region together with the residual background variance measured in the sky subtracted images. Because all exposures share identical instrumental settings and integration times, the uncertainties are dominated by background variance rather than by read noise.

For each filter, the five calibrated and background subtracted science frames were integrated using the region-sum method, and their mean flux and standard error were adopted as the final measurements. These values are listed in Table 4, and the measurements form the four points of the SED analyzed in Section 4.

3. METHODS AND ANALYSIS

This section describes the full data-processing workflow, including CCD calibration, sky-background subtraction using dedicated sky frames, region-sum photometry, uncertainty propagation, and construction of the SED. All processing was implemented in Python using `astropy`, `numpy`, and `photutils` (Collaboration 2013, 2018; Bradley et al. 2023).

3.1. CCD Calibration Frames

All raw science images were corrected using bias frames, dark frames, and flat fields taken during the same observing run. Table 2 summarizes the calibration exposures used in constructing the master calibration frames.

The SBIG STL-11000M CCD used in this study contained a KAF-11000 detector with a read noise of 13 e^- and a gain of $1.6\text{ e}^-/\text{ADU}$ in 2×2 binning mode. Though dark current increases linearly with time, due to the low operating temperatures, dark current is negligible for 120 s exposures; nonetheless, we included dark subtraction for completeness and consistency.

Master calibration frames were created by median-combining five exposures per filter to eliminate cosmic rays and unstable pixels. For the R - and I -band flats obtained in the unbinned mode, the master flats and flat-darks were resampled to 2×2 binning using bilinear interpolation to match the science-frame pixel scale.

3.2. Construction of Cleaned Science Frames

Each raw science image, O , was cleaned using the standard calibration formula:

$$C = \frac{O - D}{(F - FD)/\langle F \rangle}, \quad (1)$$

where D is the master dark, F is the master flat field, FD is the master flat-dark, and $\langle F \rangle$ denotes the mean value of the flat used to normalize the pixel response. Because the dark frames include the detector bias level, subtraction of the master dark simultaneously removes both bias and thermal signal from the science images.

This procedure removes fixed-pattern noise, thermal noise, and pixel-to-pixel sensitivity variations. After calibration, all frames were visually inspected and checked using pixel-intensity histograms to confirm the absence of large artifacts prior to background subtraction. Figure 1 shows a representative cleaned science frame in each filter.

3.3. Background Subtraction

Because the observations were taken approximately 29.53 hours after a full Moon, the calibrated science frames exhibited elevated sky background levels, particularly in the R - and I -band. Grid-based background estimation

Figure 1. Calibrated CCD images of the M33 core in the B , V , R , and I filters (left to right). Each panel shows a single exposure after bias, dark, and flat-field correction, prior to sky-background subtraction.

Table 2. Calibration frames used in CCD reduction.

Frame Type	Applies To	Count	Notes
Bias	all BVRI	20 total	Zero-exposure frames; filter independent
Dark	all BVRI	10 total	120 s exposures; matched to science frames
Flat-field	B, V, R, I	10 per filter	Twilight flats; filter dependent
Flat-dark	B, V, R, I	10 per filter	Exposure time matched to flats

techniques (e.g., `Background2D`; Team (2023)) were tested but not adopted for the final reduction. Instead, specific sky frames were obtained by offsetting the telescope 11 jog steps away from the galaxy. For each filter, the sky frames were cleaned using the same calibration procedure applied to the science images and median combined to construct a master sky frame, S_{master} .

Each calibrated science frame, C , was corrected according to

$$C' = C - \alpha S_{\text{master}}, \quad (2)$$

where the scaling factor α was chosen to match the sky brightness level in the science frame C , thus minimizing large-scale background contribution while maintaining galaxy signal in the corrected frame C' .

Figure 2 shows pixel-value histograms of representative science frames after dark subtraction, flat-field correction, and sky-background subtraction, illustrating the effect of the procedure on the global background distribution.

3.4. Region-Sum Photometry

The central light distribution of M33 was extended and not well approximated by a point-spread function, thus region-sum photometry provided a more stable measurement than small-aperture photometry.

Integrated fluxes for each filter were measured by summing the pixel values within a fixed region enclosing the central region in each background subtracted frame. The same region was applied to all filters to ensure consistent sampling of the galaxy’s central light distribution.

Flux uncertainties were estimated by propagating photon-counting noise within the extraction region and the variance of residual background pixels measured in the background subtracted images. These uncertainties reflect the background-limited nature of the measurements rather than photon-limited statistics.

The integrated fluxes and uncertainties are presented in Table 4.

3.5. SED Construction

For each band, the five calibrated and background subtracted science frames were measured photometrically using the region-sum method. The mean integrated fluxes and their standard errors were used to construct a broadband relative SED of the M33 core by associating each flux with the effective wavelength of its corresponding filter.

The resulting integrated fluxes:

$$\begin{aligned} F_B &= (6.70 \times 10^9) \pm (1.70 \times 10^9) \text{ e}^- , \\ F_V &= (5.35 \times 10^9) \pm (1.51 \times 10^9) \text{ e}^- , \\ F_R &= (2.17 \times 10^{10}) \pm (6.09 \times 10^9) \text{ e}^- , \\ F_I &= (1.44 \times 10^{11}) \pm (1.57 \times 10^{10}) \text{ e}^- . \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2. Five frames per filter of pixel-value histograms after science frames were calibrated and background subtracted. Distributions are narrower with a positive skew, reflecting the removal of large-scale background structure while preserving galaxy pixels.

And resulting fluxes per unit wavelengths:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{F_B}{\lambda} &= (6.70 \times 10^7) \pm (1.70 \times 10^7) \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}}, \\ \frac{F_V}{\lambda} &= (2.67 \times 10^7) \pm (7.57 \times 10^6) \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}}, \\ \frac{F_R}{\lambda} &= (8.67 \times 10^7) \pm (2.44 \times 10^7) \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}}, \\ \frac{F_I}{\lambda} &= (7.22 \times 10^8) \pm (7.86 \times 10^7) \frac{e^-}{\text{nm}}. \end{aligned}$$

To test for statistical significance in the spectral slope of the constructed SED, we used:

$$z = \left| \frac{x_1 - x_2}{\sqrt{\sigma_{x_1}^2 + \sigma_{x_2}^2}} \right| \quad (3)$$

$|z| \leq 2.1$: No significant difference,
 $2.1 < |z| < 2.5$: Marginally significant,
 $|z| \geq 2.5$: Statistically significant,

Table 3. Residual background statistics in the *BVRI* science frames after sky-background subtraction.

Filter	Median Residual (ADU)	Std. Dev. (ADU)
<i>B</i>	$(0.8 \pm 0.3) \times 10^6$	6.9×10^6
<i>V</i>	$(1.1 \pm 0.4) \times 10^6$	8.1×10^6
<i>R</i>	$(1.7 \pm 0.5) \times 10^6$	1.4×10^7
<i>I</i>	$(1.9 \pm 0.7) \times 10^6$	1.8×10^7

where x_1 and x_2 are the fluxes per unit wavelength in electron counts per nm, and σ_{x_1} and σ_{x_2} are the respective uncertainties of the fluxes per unit wavelength. A statistical Z-test value more than 2.5 would indicate that the observed result is more than 2.5 standard deviations of the mean.

3.6. Core-Color Check (aperture diagnostic in *B* and *V*)

As an independent diagnostic of the core’s color, we measured the central region using circular-aperture photometry in the *B* and *V* bands on the fully processed, sky subtracted science frames. For each filter, we summed the net counts within a circular aperture of radius 60 pixels centered on the core, with the local background estimated from several nearby background boxes and subtracted frame by frame. The same aperture geometry was adopted across the five exposures, from these measurements we compute the instrumental core flux ratio:

$$\frac{F_B}{F_V} = 0.2485 \pm 0.0094,$$

and the corresponding instrumental color:

$$(b - v) \equiv -2.5 \log_{10} \left(\frac{F_B}{F_V} \right) = 1.512 \pm 0.041,$$

where the quoted uncertainties are propagated from the frame-to-frame scatter and background variance. Because no standard-star zeropoints or extinction corrections are applied, this color is reported in instrumental units and is used only as a qualitative consistency check on the relative redness of the core.

4. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows pixel-value histograms of the calibrated science frames in each filter after background subtraction. Prior to subtraction, the histograms show strong positive skew with broad wings, most pronounced in the *R* and *I* bands due to elevated moonlight background. After subtraction, the distributions are narrower and closer to Gaussian, while remaining a strong positive skew, as expected for a bright galaxy. The reduced width and minor negative tails indicate effective removal of the large-scale sky background.

Table 3 summarizes the median background level and standard deviation after subtraction to quantify the residual background. All median residuals lie $\pm 2 \times 10^6$ well below the integrated flux of the galaxy’s core and are consistent with background-limited noise. The increase toward longer wavelengths is consistent with enhanced lunar contamination in the *R* and *I* bands.

4.1. Integrated Fluxes

Table 4 summarizes the integrated fluxes and associated uncertainties of the M33 core measured in each filter using region-sum photometry.

Table 4. Region-sum photometry measurements of the M33 core used to construct the relative BVRI SED.

Filter	λ_{eff} (nm)	Integrated Flux (ADU)	Uncertainty (ADU)	F/F_V
<i>B</i>	438	4.19×10^9	1.06×10^9	1.25 ± 0.46
<i>V</i>	545	3.34×10^9	9.46×10^8	1.00
<i>R</i>	641	1.35×10^{10}	3.81×10^9	4.04 ± 1.49
<i>I</i>	798	9.02×10^{10}	9.83×10^9	27.01 ± 8.64

Note. Integrated fluxes are net instrumental counts (ADU) measured from sky subtracted frames using a fixed region enclosing the central light concentration. Uncertainties reflect the standard error across the five calibrated exposures per filter and incorporate residual background variance. The normalized ratios F/F_V are dimensionless and are included to emphasize the relative SED shape. No absolute photometric calibration is applied; results are interpreted in terms of relative broadband trends.

Table 5. The mean total flux in electron counts with calculated signal-to-noise ratios for each BVRI filter

Filter	Mean Total Flux (e^-)	Uncertainty (e^-)	$(S/N)_{dB}$
<i>B</i>	6.7×10^9	1.69×10^9	49.1
<i>V</i>	5.35×10^9	1.51×10^9	48.6
<i>R</i>	2.17×10^{10}	6.09×10^9	51.7
<i>I</i>	1.4×10^{11}	1.57×10^{10}	55.8

Note. The signal-to-noise ratio (S/N) follows Poisson Statistics, where $\sigma \sim \sqrt{flux}$ for photon counting. The linear S/N is calculated using $\frac{F}{\sqrt{F}}$ and converted to decibels $(S/N)_{dB}$ using a base-10 logarithm.

4.2. Spectral Energy Distribution

Figure 3 presents the relative SED of the M33 core constructed from the integrated *BVRI* flux measurements. All observations were obtained with the same instrument, extraction region, and observing conditions, making the relative flux calibration across filters sound despite the absence of an absolute photometric zero-point. The SED exhibits several clear features:

- A statistically insignificant, $z = 2.1$, drop in flux from the *B*- to *V*- band, resulting in a relatively flat spectral slope,
- A marginal statistical significance, $z = 2.4$, increase in flux from the *V*- to *R*- band, resulting in a slight upward slope,
- A statistically significant, $z = 7.7$, rise towards the *I*-band, with the *I*-band flux an order of magnitude higher than in the *V*-band.

These trends show a statistical monotonic increase towards the R and I optical bands, with effectively flat B and V bands.

4.3. Core-color check in B and V

The performed *B/V* core-color check produced a core flux ratio $F_B/F_V = 0.2485 \pm 0.0094$, corresponding to an instrumental color $(b - v) = 1.512 \pm 0.041$.

5. DISCUSSION

The integrated *BVRI* photometry of M33's central region reveals a SED that rises monotonically toward longer optical wavelengths, with a relatively flat *B–V* slope and a pronounced increase through the *R*- and *I*-band. Consistency of the core's color with an evolved population is proved in the aperture-based *B/V* diagnostic and verifies the direction of the SED slope at short wavelengths. The $(b - v) = 1.512 \pm 0.041$ implies substantially weaker blue emissions relative to *V* in the central region; consistent with the red-enhanced SED shape. While this quantity is not tied to an absolute photometric system, its sign and magnitude provides a complete internal check: the core is red, as

Figure 3. Circular points on the graph mark the average wavelength of the B, V, R, and I filter, from left to right. The vertical axis shows net integrated instrumental counts in analog-to-digital units; no absolute photometric calibration (e.g., standard-star zeropoints) is applied. Error bars represent the propagated measurement uncertainties across the five exposures. We interpret the SED in terms of relative shape of the strong redward rise from *V* through *R* to *I*, rather than as an absolute flux-density spectrum.

expected for a luminosity-weighted population dominated by evolved stars. Together, with the statistically substantial increase at longer wavelengths, the red-ward rise is qualitatively supported with population-synthesis expectations for late-type spiral galaxy nuclei.

Comparison to observed SED shapes from published stellar population synthesis models and empirical templates (e.g., Bruzual & Charlot 2003; Maraston 2005) suggests that the dominant stellar population in the core of M33 is indicative of a characteristic age of 10–13 Gyr. The steep rise toward the *I*-band is consistent with substantial contributions from red giant branch and asymptotic giant branch stars, which dominate the optical and near-infrared light of evolved stellar populations. This inferred age range is broadly consistent with previous resolved-star and integrated-light studies of M33’s inner regions, despite the galaxy’s classification as a late-type spiral lacking a prominent classical bulge.

It should be noted that Doppler shift was tested using the linear formula and determined to be negligible due to M33’s relative closeness to the Milky Way Galaxy. M33 is in the Local Group with a net negative radial velocity (v) of approximately -200 km/s, producing a wavelength shift ($\Delta\lambda$) of less than 1 nm. (University of Nevada (2021))

$$\Delta\lambda = \left| \lambda_0 \left(\frac{v}{c} \right) \right| \leq 1 \text{ nm} \quad (4)$$

The absence of the ultraviolet (*U*)-band in this analysis reflects both observational and scientific considerations. The *U*-band is particularly sensitive to atmospheric extinction and variable sky brightness, which would have been greatly affected by the bright lunar conditions. And while the *U*-band flux would be useful in probing younger stellar populations, it provides minimal leverage in constraining the age of older stellar populations.

The observations were obtained under bright-sky conditions approximately 29.53 hours after a full Moon, leading to elevated background levels, particularly in the *R*- and *I*-band. These conditions motivated the use of dedicated offset sky frames for background subtraction to ensure the measured emissions were from the galaxy alone. Grid-based background estimation techniques were tested but found to over-subtract diffuse galactic light in the inner regions. Sky-frame subtraction, by contrast, effectively removed large-scale background structure while preserving extended emission.

Pixel-value histograms provided an independent diagnostic of the background subtraction performance, showing a collapse of the background distributions toward zero after subtraction with substantially reduced width. Although the intrinsic brightness of the M33 core implies an extremely high photon-limited signal-to-noise ratio, the effective uncertainties in the integrated flux measurements are dominated by residual background variance. Because the extraction region spans many thousands of pixels and the source is spatially extended, small residual background fluctuations accumulate and set the practical noise floor. Therefore, the resulting measurements reflect the background-limited nature of ground-based CCD photometry of extended sources rather than photon-counting statistics.

Despite these limitations, the recovered SED retains sufficient precision to distinguish the overall shape of the central stellar population and to place meaningful constraints on its evolutionary state. We tested a catalog-based photometric calibration by cross-matching field stars in our image to Gaia DR3 sources (queried via astroquery) and applying published Gaia-to-Johnson-Cousins color transformations to estimate B and V zeropoints (Vallenari et al. (2023); Ginsburg et al. (2019); Ruelas-Mayorga et al. (2025)). In practice, the calibration proved sensitive to star selection and local background structure in this crowded field, and the approach was not fully consistent with our extended-source region-sum measurement approach. We therefore do not adopt an absolute zeropoint calibration for the galaxy core. Instead, we present the $BVRI$ SED in instrumental units (ADU) and include an internal B/V aperture-based core-color diagnostic for a dynamic check.

Future observations under darker sky conditions, with expanded wavelength coverage and improved background characterization, would enable more precise age constraints and allow exploration of additional stellar population properties. We note that broadband optical SEDs are subject to age-metallicity degeneracy, and while other methods provide greater galaxy-wide precision, the significant redward rise in the core is indicative of an evolved central population. Nevertheless, this study demonstrates that background subtraction combined with region-sum photometry provides a robust framework for extracting stellar population information from ground-based observations of extended galactic systems.

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